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Reward System and Organizational Performance

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Abstract

The study examined reward systems and organizational performance. This was done in the measures of reward system, compensation policy, and performance recognition for the organization's performance at Delta State University. Responses from respondents were retrieved with the aid of a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire. A survey research design was employed in this study, and the stratified random sampling method was also adopted to administer 367 staff members from Delta State University. The questionnaire was coded with the aid of a spread sheet, and the respondents profiles were analyzed manually using a simple percentage approach. The research questions were analyzed with the aid of descriptive statistics, and the hypotheses of the study were tested using multiple regression analysis with the aid of SPSS. The results from the analysis revealed that the dimensions of reward systems (compensation policy and performance recognition) in this study have significant and positive effects on organizational performance. The study concludes that a good reward system provides positive assurance for fulfilling the needs and wants of employees in the workplace. It generally has an optimistic attitude behind it, and it is generally given to have good leverage to satisfy the psychological requirements of employees. The goal of the study was to make a recommendation about how employee recognition, when considered from formal, informal, and day-to-day perspectives, could inspire staff to ensure high performance in tertiary institutions. Therefore, it is advised that the management of tertiary institutions devote trustworthy resources to the development and implementation of employee recognition programs in order to produce the desired results. The study also recommends that management view employee recognition as a significant investment rather than one of the pricey and unnecessary practices that offer little value to tertiary institutions.

Key Words: Compensation Employee, Development, Management, Performance, Recognition and Rewards.

INTRODUCTION

Reward systems are becoming a powerful tool for managing firms in the context of globalization. Ezigbo (2021) argues that globalization requires proactive, innovative, creative, and strategic business management to survive competition. Reward systems are important for talent attraction and retention, as they show value and motivate employees to do a good job. The right compensation plan includes benefits and bonuses and invests employees in the work being done, giving them a stronger sense of satisfaction when the company succeeds (Bayon, 2019).

Organizations use human resources to gain a competitive advantage and achieve objectives. HRM is a strategic approach that emphasizes a 'tight fit' between individual needs, rights, ambitions, and goals. It is an asset that

should be invested in to provide long-term commitment and high performance. Employees aim to achieve individual goals while working for the organization. Compensation and reward systems provide a platform for equity and fairness, creating a challenging environment and increasing productivity. It ensures both intrinsic and extrinsic needs are met (Bayon, 2019).

Organizations often focus on other resources instead of remuneration, leading to a lack of attention to employee reward policies, which can lead to high turnover and negatively affect organizational success. Organizations strive to achieve their corporate goals, but productivity is more dependent on the attitude and morale of the workers. Low productivity is a problem in many developing countries, and business owners are looking for improvements in quality while reducing costs. This has led to conflicts between employees and management.

Reward management is an effective way to motivate workers and maximize the utilization of human resources, leading to the realization of the organization's goals. This study seeks to determine the effect of reward systems on organizational performance.

The major objective of the study is to assess the impact of the reward system on organizational performance; the specific objectives are to: determine if compensation policy has a significant effect on organizational performance; ascertain if performance recognition has a significant effect on organizational performance; and examine the effect of extrinsic rewards on organizational performance. The study is organized into five sections for ease of understanding by the readers. Section one is the introduction; section two is the review of the related literature; section three is the material and method; section four is the data analysis and interpretation; and section five and the last section are the conclusion and recommendations.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Concept of Reward System

A reward system is a payment or reward given to employees (Armstrong & Murlins, 2012). A reward system is a system to reward performance and motivate employees, but it must be timely and tied to effective performance. It is the major link in the exchange process between individual workers and the organization. Employees are rewarded for their contributions with tangible and intangible packages, such as pay raises, bonuses, company automobiles, vacation benefits, and more.

The basic reward is the employee's salary or wage, which may be an hourly wage, a set amount of pay per month, or commission-based. Reward systems must be designed to motivate workers, as motivation is essential for high performance (Armstrong, 2012).

Compensation Policy

Compensation policy influences employee decisions and relationships (Ira, 2010; Kwon, 2001; Armstrong, 2007). It reflects an organization's values, culture, and philosophy and helps define employment relationships, contractual obligations, and the implied psychological contract between the employer and employee (Zacher, 2015).

Armstrong (2007) and Ombasa (2013) both emphasize the importance of creating a compensation policy that takes into account internal and external factors such as industrial practice, market considerations, and HR strategy. Compensation policy is based on factors such as grade, pay structure, total reward, and philosophies and values to ensure competitiveness, equity, and transparency.

Armstrong (2007) suggests that organizational objectives and strategy influence compensation policy, with growth visions having a long-term policy and non-growth visions having a short-term policy. HR strategies and practices, such as skill retention, attraction, and talent management, also influence compensation policy.

Armstrong (2007), Meyar & Becker (2004), Chew & Chen (2008), and Anvari (2011) all discuss the influence of market and industrial practices on compensation policies. Intrinsic compensation provides a long-term relationship and commitment, while extrinsic compensation has an exchange effect. Performance-based or pay-skill-performance HR strategies will advocate for compensation policies that are aligned to training, skills, and performance.

Armstrong (2007) and Meyer & Allen (2007) suggest that organizations should adopt compensation policies based on market leadership to prevent "poaching" of valued employees and make competitors less attractive. Trade unions use joint negotiations to create compensation policies, while the government sets minimum wage guidelines and enforces government benefits guidelines on social security, health, and pensions. Non-compliance results in fines and litigation.

Employee commitment is an internal psychological force that makes an employee feel ready to work, accomplish tasks, stick to the organization, and speak positively about the organization (Ira, 2010). Meyer et al. (2001) and Noble et al. (1999) have both defined commitment as a force that makes an individual stick to a course of action relevant to a particular goal. Pare et al. (2007) have also identified it as associated with behaviors of high involvement, reduced intentions of opting out of the organization, going the extra mile to accomplish duties and tasks, willingness to help and uplift others at work, and corporate citizenship.

Meyer and Allen (1991) identified three forms of employee commitment: affective, continuance, and normative. Affective commitment is linked to emotional attachment, identification, and involvement, while continuance is linked to opportunity cost. Normative commitment is based on reciprocity and the feeling of being indebted to the organization. Cohen (2003) found that organizational commitment is influenced by values, morals, performance, compliance, and culture.

Pare et al. (2007) posit that the different forms and dimensions of commitment are critical in the development of HR strategies, policies, and practices aimed at increasing commitment at the workplace. Thus, the philosophy of compensation policy is largely guided by values of transparency, compliance, and performance (Zacher et al., 2005).

Performance Recognition

Recognition means acknowledging someone before their peers for specific accomplishments achieved, actions taken, or attitudes exemplified through their behavior. Recognition and appreciation can also be combined as an approach to reward systems in the form of a public statement of thanks in the eyes of the employees, co-workers, or team. Citing specific examples of what they have done that has positively impacted the organization, Jefferies (1997) stated that organizations should retain their best employees by recognizing their contributions to the organization. She argued that recognition motivates employees as it involves acknowledgment of the extra effort. Recognition can reduce pessimism that hinders performance and productivity. Curran (2004) acknowledges employees efforts more personally, more locally, and more frequently through recognition, which lifts employee motivation and improves overall organizational morale.

Jefferies (1997) argues that organizations can benefit from a motivated workforce by just recognizing the employee through a simple, genuine, spoken thank you. Romano (2003) encourages managers to use recognition as a factor that will strengthen the bond between the employees and the organization. Jefferies (1997) supports Nelson (1994) in affirming that recognition does not have to be expensive but emphasizes that it must be consistent and perceived as a long-term commitment by the organization. Wiscombe (2002) recognized that high-performance organizations (HPO) have always understood the importance of offering awards and incentives that recognize, validate, and value outstanding work. Recognition programs have the purpose of keeping employees motivated and productive and are seen as effective methods of reinforcing company expectations and goals. Recognition and appreciation are integral components of a winning reward strategy.

Extrinsic Rewards

The extrinsic rewards cover the basic needs of income to survive (to pay bills), a feeling of stability and consistency (the job is secure), and recognition (my workplace values my skills). Hellriegel (1999) says an extrinsic reward is an outcome supplied by the organization and includes salary, status, job security, and fringe benefits. One can compare these rewards to the job context items that Herzberg called hygiene factors. According to Baron (1983), cited in Eshak et al. (2016), extrinsic rewards are tangible rewards, and the rewards

are external to the job or tasks performed by the employee. They can be in terms of salary or pay, incentives, bonuses, promotion, and job security. They are also called financial rewards.

To Luthans (2000), they mean pay for performance, such as performance bonuses, job promotions, commissions, tips, gratitude, gifts, etc. McCormick (1999) defined extrinsic rewards as those that are external to the task of the job, such as pay, work conditions, fringe benefits, security, promotion, a contract of service, the work environment, and the condition of work. He noted that such tangible rewards are often determined at the organizational level and may be largely outside the control of individual managers. In his opinion, other things included are competitive salaries and wages, increments in pay, bonuses, and such indirect forms of payment. However, Bard (2006) noted that caution must be exercised while applying an extrinsic reward system to employees. In his opinion, it is those within lower-level positions in the organization that are more susceptible to extrinsic motivational factors than those within higher-level positions.

The reason, according to him, is that those in lower-level positions tend to have lower wages than those in higher-level positions, which explains the need for extrinsic rewards that have some form of monetary component. It can actually lead to an increase in one's base wage, resulting in a happier and more productive employee. Merchant (2007) observed that there are three main categories of the financial or monetary part of reward systems. They include performance-based salary increases, which organizations pay to their employees after a very fixed period of time. Merchant (2007) noted that it is called a performance-based salary increment. Another is called a short-term incentive plan. It is a cash bonus given mostly to managerial-level staff based on performance over a short period of time. The last one is the long-term incentive plan. It is a reward that is based on performance that is measured over longer periods of time. By using the plan, a company can reward employees for their great work performance to maximize the firm's long-term value. It also helps to attract and retain good talent for the organization (Merchant, 2007). Emeka, Amaka, and Ejim (2017) posit that all extrinsic factors enhance the motivation of employees, which ultimately influences them positively to perform effectively towards the realization of organizational goals and objectives.

Concept of Organizational Performance

Armstronge (2008) posits that reward plays a vital role in increasing employees' performance in the organization. He further stated that it is a means of getting better results by understanding and managing performance within an agreed-upon framework of planned goals, standards, and competency requirements. According to Siti-Nabiha, Thum, and Sardina (2012), a reward, especially a payment reward, is usually something valuable, such as money. Organizational performance is the analysis of a company's performance against its objectives and goals, focusing on shareholder value, financial performance, and market performance. The term has a similar meaning to "organizational effectiveness". However, "organizational effectiveness" covers a broader area. Let's look at the meaning of the two words. Organizational is the adjective for "organization." An organization is an organized group of individuals with a specific purpose. 'Performance' is the process of performing a function or task. We perceive it as how successfully the person carries out that function. When we put the two words together, i.e., organizational performance, what do they mean? According to Louise James, a senior manager at Pitcher Partners "organizational performance refers to how successfully an organized group of people with a particular purpose performs a function". Thus, organizational performance can be measured as follows:

Financial performance: This refers to measuring a company's operations and policies in monetary terms. In other words, in terms of value in Naira, dollars, pounds, euros, etc. We can see how good a firm's financial performance is by looking at its return on assets and return on investment. We can also gauge its financial performance by measuring value added.

Market Performance: This measures how well a company or product performs in the marketplace. In other words, whether a product's market share has risen, if product upgrades help boost sales, etc. When we are talking specifically about a product rather than the whole company, we say "product market performance".

Shareholder Value: This performance looks at how much a company enriches its shareholders. In fact, many say it is the ultimate organizational performance measure. Shareholder value maximization and shareholder value models mean the same thing as shareholder value. Shareholder value may also refer to a company's market capitalization.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Researchers' Model (2023).

Theoretical Underpin

Human Capital Theory: Resick (2007) states that human capital signifies the combined intelligence and experience of staff as a source of competitive advantage that cannot be imitated by rivals. This theory has implications for attracting, engaging, rewarding, and developing people in organizations. The theory has cross-cutting significance in HRD practices. The theory has been criticized for not addressing other underlying components of employee performance. Scholars have argued that ultimately, it is only the characteristics that enhance employee performance that should be used to address HRD practices. The theory is relevant to this study. This is because it considers the intelligence and experience of staff. This means that those with the desired intelligence and experience are able to develop in an organization with ease.

Review of Related Empirical Studies

Studies on compensation management and organizational performance have elicited intensified research. The importance of employees' commitment to the organization's objectives and how to ensure that compensation policy contributes to desired behavior are now central concerns for organizations. HR practitioners and academic researchers have embarked on cross-sectional and case studies to investigate the lines between compensation policy and employee commitment.

Rizal et al. (2014) investigated the effect of compensation on motivation, employee commitment to the organization, and employee performance at a local revenue management organization in Indonesia. The data collected from respondents was analyzed using a structural equation model. The findings of the research were that compensation significantly affects employees' motivation and their commitment to the organization but does not have a significant effect on employee performance. Commitment was, however, found to have a significant influence on employee performance.

Ibojo and Asabi (2014) examined the extent to which compensation management affects employee performance, the relationship between working conditions and employee performance, the rate at which welfare services affect employee performance, the relationship between compensation management and improved productivity, and the relationship between compensation management and staff retention. Responses obtained

from the Likert-type questionnaire design for the study were analyzed using a frequency table and analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results showed a significant relationship between good welfare service and employee performance; compensation management and improved productivity; and compensation management and employee performance. The study thus posits that compensation management has a positive effect on employee performance.

Ayesha, Amna, Tahleel, and Hina (2015) constructed a structured questionnaire with which they obtained data to study the effects of compensation and motivation on employee performance. Using a sample of the banking sector in Faisalabad, the simple regression model revealed that incentive and motivation have a significant effect on employee performance.

Oladejo and Oluwaseun (2014) examined the effect of compensation plans on workers performance in Nigerian food and beverage manufacturing companies using a sample of 125 questionnaires administered and distributed to the staff of the selected food and beverage companies in Lagos State. Analyses from the frequency table, percentage, and Chi-square test showed that compensation plans have a significant and positive effect on workers performance.

Hameed, Muhammad, Hafiz, Ghazanfar, and Muhammad (2014) examined the impact of compensation on employee performance at banks in Pakistan. A questionnaire was designed to collect data on factors related to compensation like salary, rewards, indirect compensation, and employee performance. Findings from correlation and regression analyses showed that compensation has a positive impact on employee performance.

Nnorom, Akpa, Egwuonwu, Akintaro, Shonubi, and Herbertson (2016) examined the effect of compensation administration on employee productivity. The data gathered from the structured questionnaire of 50 respondents at Dangote Nigeria Headquarters in Lagos, Nigeria, revealed that effective compensation administration has a significant positive effect on employee productivity. Using a sample of 126 workers at the Local Apparatus Work Unit (LAWU).

Kendari, Muhamad, Idrus, Djumahir, & Mintarti (2014) investigated the effect of compensation on motivation and organizational commitment on employee performance. The data analysis from the SEM (Structural Equation Model) indicated that compensation has a significant effect on motivation and organizational commitment but does not have a significant effect on employee performance. The study posits that compensation cannot directly improve employee performance, thus contradicting the earlier assertions that compensation has a direct effect on performance.

All the studies reviewed indicated that compensation management has a significant effect on organizational performance. Although most of the studies did not examine the extent to which compensation management has impacted the organization's performance or the function or level of management at which compensation has been studied, this has created a research gap. Also, none of the studies discussed the human resource as a capital asset, a view held high in this contemporary era. Thus, this research tends to examine the management of compensation right from the planning stage of policy design, its incorporation of involvement, openness, and performance-based compensation, and how this has in turn contributed to the commitment of employees to their work.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study used a survey research design, which entails surveying people and recording their responses for analysis. This method was deemed to be the most suitable for this study because the problem at hand involves people's perceptions, opinions, or attitudes, none of which can be measured directly because we cannot see them.

To better understand the relationships between the variables in the research problem, this study used both quantitative and qualitative research approaches within the survey research design. The study population was the academic staff of Delta State University Abraka, with a population size of 4193 members. A sample size of 367 respondents from a population of 4193 members using Yamane's (1968) sample size calculation formula, where the study's appropriateness and representation were determined.

The stratified sampling method was used to distribute the 367-person sample size among the institutions according to their locations in order to fairly represent the organizations. Primary data was obtained through the use of a self-structured questionnaire with an adjusted Likert scale of five (5) points. Both primary and secondary processing of the retrieved data were done manually. Editing, classification, coding, transcription, and tabulation were all part of the processing stage. In the data analysis, regression and Pearson's correlation coefficient were used to find the relationship between the variables in the hypothesis and the effects of rewards on organizational performance. Descriptive analysis was also used to determine the current reward system used in the educational sector. For this, the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 23 was used on a computer. The data was presented in tables after manual analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

Information was gathered through a questionnaire given to the employees of Delta State University. First is the data analysis, which comprises the correlation and regression analysis of other research data. Second is the discussion of the results of the data analysis for the study.

Data Analysis

Correlation Matrix: Correlation analysis is used to examine the relationship between dependent and independent variables. Its values lie between -1 and +1. +1 indicates that there is a positive linear sense between two variables that are perfectly related, while -1 indicates a negative linear sense between two variables. This tells the degree of correlation between the independent and dependent variables, whether there is a moderate or low degree of correlation.

Table 1: Pearson Correlation

		OP	CP	PR	ER
Pearson Correlation	CP	1.000			
	PR	.297	1.000		
	ER	.190	.449	1.000	
	OP	.214	.546	.574	1.000

Source: SPSS Output, 2023.

The Pearson correlation in Table 1 showed the coefficient of the type of relationship that exists between the independent variables "Compensation Policy (CP), Performance Recognition (PR), and Extrinsic Reward (ER)" and the dependent variable "Organizational Performance (OP)".

CP has a coefficient of $r = 0.297 > 0.05$, which reveals that CP has a strong positive correlation with OP. PR has a coefficient of ($r = 0.214 > 0.05$), which reveals that PR has a strong positive correlation with OP. This implies that an increase in PR would have positive effects on OP at Delta State University. ER has a coefficient of ($r = 0.190 > 0.05$), which reveals that ER has a strong positive correlation with OP. This implies that an increase in ER would have positive effects on OP at Delta State University.

The study is focused on enhancing organizational performance through reward systems. The results of the correlation analysis involving all the dimensions of the reward system reported positive correlation coefficient values among the measures. This indicated that they are appropriate dimensions of the reward system.

Table 2: Multiple Regression Analysis of Measures of Reward System and Organizational Performance Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.602	.773		7.243	.000
	CP	.029	.014	.028	2.071	.003
	PR	.119	.029	.118	4.103	.001
	ER	.037	.016	.039	2.313	.004

a. Dependent Variable: OP

Table 3: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.938 ^a	.880	.840	1.369	1.280

a. Predictors: (Constant), CP, PR, ER

b. Dependent Variable: OP

Table 4: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	805.548	4	201.387	107.428	.000 ^b
	Residual	672.988	359	1.875		
	Total	1478.536	363			

a. Dependent Variable: OP

c. Predictors: (Constant), CP, PR, ER

Source: SPSS Output, 2023

The result from table 2 is that the p-value is less than 0.005, which shows a positive value of 0.028, which shows that compensation policy (CP) has a significant effect on organizational performance as the probability of 0.003 is also less than the critical level of significance ($p < 0.005$). With the statistics, we reject the null hypotheses and accept the alternative hypotheses; therefore, CP has significant effects on organizational performance (OP). In the regression result from Table 2, the p-value is less than 0.005, which shows a positive value of 0.118, which shows that performance recognition (PR) has a significant effect on organizational performance as the probability of 0.001 is also less than the critical level of significance ($p < 0.005$). With the statistics, we reject the null hypotheses and accept the alternative hypotheses; therefore, PR has significant effects on OP.

In the regression result from Table 2, the p-value is less than 0.005, which shows a positive value of 0.039, which shows that extrinsic reward (ER) has a significant effect on OP as the probability of 0.004 is also less than the critical level of significance ($p < 0.005$). With the statistics, we reject the null hypotheses and accept the alternative hypotheses; therefore, ER has significant effects on OP.

The results from the multiple regression analysis recorded the effects of the system and organizational performance of Delta State University. The three variables to measure the reward system are CP, PR, and ER, which exhibited statistically significant positive effects on OP.

Conclusion

A good reward system provides positive assurance for fulfilling the needs and wants of employees in the workplace. It generally has an optimistic attitude behind it, and it is generally given good leverage to satisfy the psychological requirements of employees. As earlier mentioned in the body of the work, the elements of a reward system include: pay raises, bonuses, company automobiles, vacation benefits, well-furnished offices, jobs with higher responsibilities, a sense of worth, recognition, health insurance plans, club privileges, child

care support, job autonomy, wall plaques, non-verbal signals such as smiles, golden handshakes, profit sharing, incentive plans, developmental feedback, and so on.

Rewards are basically an act or promise for greater action. It is like a stimulus for greater action. It means additional remuneration or benefit to an employee in recognition of achievement or better work. It is a spur or zeal in the employees for better performance. Therefore, a hope for a reward is a powerful incentive to motivate employees because these rewards are used in organizations to induce the performance of employees to be effective and efficient in the workplace so as to achieve the desired aims and objectives of the organization. Each company or organization must decide if increased performance or satisfactory levels of performance are to be remunerated by employees' salaries alone or if additional financial rewards are to be considered. The ultimate goal is to increase performance by reinforcing specific behaviors through the available reward system. The strategic objective for all organizations lies in an effective approach. Most organizations are continually challenged with achieving the aims and objectives of their desired organizational goals and objectives. Organizational heads or managers need to attract, motivate, retain, and satisfy their employees. This is the greatest guarantee for organizational success and performance.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the study recommends the following:

The researchers advise that institutional policies that are employee-driven and take into account the unique needs of academic staff members in terms of their physical and psychological needs should be developed and implemented by government and university authorities. This includes, among other things, granting academic staff authority to conduct essential academic and administrative tasks within public universities without interference from the government. According to the researcher, such factors will safeguard academic staff members' autonomy and interests, which will ultimately lead to higher levels of job satisfaction and, as a result, better organizational performance.

A crucial and fundamental foundation for raising the level of commitment at work is the continuous development of informal mechanisms like employee involvement cultures, which tertiary institutions should actively pursue.

The goal of the study was to make a recommendation about how employee recognition, when considered from formal, informal, and day-to-day perspectives, could inspire staff to ensure high performance in tertiary institutions. Therefore, it is advised that the management of tertiary institutions devote trustworthy resources to the development and implementation of employee recognition programs in order to produce the desired results. Lastly, the study makes the suggestion that management view employee recognition as a significant investment rather than one of the pricey and unnecessary practices that offer little value to tertiary institutions.

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